

Mentoring on Women's Micro Enterprises, Blendi Yumi Sari as Icon of Minggirsari Village, Kanigoro District, Blitar Regency

Ayun Maduwinarti¹, Rini Rahayu Sihmawati²

^{1,2}Universitas 17 Agustus 1945 Surabaya

ayunmaduwinarti@untag-sby.ac.id¹, riniarahayus@untag-sby.ac.id²

Abstract

Minggirsari Village is one of the villages in Kanigoro District, Blitar Regency which has quite high quality Natural Resources and Human Resources. In the culinary sector, Minggirsari Village has produced Blendi 'Yumi Sari' which is processed from Minggirsari's signature long beans. The long beans used are organic long beans produced from the Association of Farmers Groups (Gapoktan) of Minggirsari Village. This blendi vegetable is often sought after by overseas Blitar people, so it is often called Blitar miss food. Vegetable blendi by the people of Blitar is still processed traditionally, so it cannot be produced in large quantities because it is constrained in terms of preservation so that it can last a long time if produced in large quantities. The purpose of this community service is to provide assistance to UMK Blendi Yumisari to develop better in terms of quality and quantity. The method used in this service is to go directly to the production process so that you can find out what needs are needed to improve the quality and quantity of blendi vegetable products. The result of this community service is to facilitate appropriate technology in the form of equipment as well as assistance and training so that it can improve its business products and the income of the Yumisari blendi business actor will increase.

Keywords: *Appropriate technology, Blendi Yumisari, Minggirsari Village*

A. Introduction

Minggirsari Village is one of the villages in Kanigoro District, Blitar Regency, East Java Province which has high quality Natural Resources and Human Resources. The wealth of natural resources and human resources is shown in the form of very abundant crops and

vegetable crops, coupled with the cohesiveness of PKK women and sub-district employees which makes Minggirsari Village very prosperous. In addition, this village is also a pilot village with the concept of Urban Farming. In general, the livelihoods of the people of Minggirsari Village can be identified into several sectors, namely agriculture, services and trade, industry, private employees, civil servants and others.

This Community Partnership Program is addressed to Blendi Yumi Sari's UMK partners located in Minggirsari village, Kanigoro sub-district, Blitar district, East Java, where the majority of business owners are women. They try and be creative to empower themselves in an effort to improve family welfare

B. Methods

Based on the problems faced by micro business partners, namely Blendi Yumi Sari, the implementation method used to solve problems faced by partners is as follows:

1. Data Collection Techniques

Technical data collection is done by means of interviews and discussions with partners. Discussions were held to get each other and provide solutions by providing input related to making vegetable blendi.

2. Approach Method

- a) Method The approach taken at the time training and mentoring is the Learning By Doing method. In this method partners do not have to leave their jobs when participating in training. It is hoped that the training provided can be received and implemented properly.
- b) The Participatory Method, which is applied in the training and mentoring process, involves the Partners directly in the application.

C. Results and Discussion

UMK Blendi Yumi Sari is a processed long beans typical of Minggirsari. The long beans used are organic products from the Association of Farmers (Gapoktan) of Minggirsari Village. Blendi packaging uses a small bag that adds to the uniqueness of Blendi products.

The origin of the name "Blendi" comes from the term vegetable for the people of Blitar with a spicy and dried taste. The specialty of blendi is its spicy, sweet, and savory taste. Another characteristic of this long bean blend vegetable is the addition of cayenne pepper, tomato and curly chili which was also developed by Minggirsari Gapoktan which develops organic farming. Organic farming in Minggrisari is managed with organic fertilizer produced by Gapoktan under the Sari Alam brand.

One of the owners of Blendi Yumi Sari UMK is Mrs. Niswatul Afifah. As a housewife, she is creative to process long beans into long bean blend. Blendi itself is very liked by the people of Blitar and has become a village icon. This food can be processed dry to keep it durable and half dry (slightly gravy). The result of Niswatul Afifah's efforts was named Yumi Sari. This Blitar specialty vegetable blend is not only made from long beans, but also made from young papaya, eggplant, young jackfruit and so on according to taste.

Mrs. Niswatul Afifah does not only make blendi food products, but also other organic food products such as bitter melon crackers without bitter taste.

The problems faced by partners are divided into 3 aspects, namely the production aspect, where the quantity of blendi products produced is very limited and the product quality is less attractive. Aspects of business management and bookkeeping, where partners are still unable to implement business management, as evidenced by the mixing between business and household expenses, income and expenses are also not recorded. The manpower management pattern and payroll system are still incidental in nature and the job descriptions are not permanent, meaning that some workers are still working odd jobs. Marketing aspect, Marketing that has been carried out so far is still conventional. Product marketing reach is still local in the Minggirsari area. Products are deposited in shops near the house. Not yet utilizing social media and also not using online marketing, while in the current era consumers prefer to make purchases online. Online marketing seems to be far more profitable than traditional marketing.

To help the problems faced by the residents, this service has the following external targets:

1. In order for MSE partners to improve the quality and quantity of their products, as well as the added value of their products, 1 electric oven and a vacuum packaging machine (vaccumsealer) are provided.
2. Increasing the ability of business management and the availability of books and records of business activities on a regular basis. By conducting training activities and business management assistance and bookkeeping as well as training using machines and equipment.
3. Training and mentoring on blendi production
4. Training and assistance in the use of social media and online marketing.

In this service, the researchers offer several solutions to deal with managerial problems faced by the village, namely:

1. Procurement of an electric oven to replace the manual oven so that the heat (temperature) can be evenly distributed to dry the long bean blended vegetables.
2. Procurement of vacuum sealer to remove air that causes bacterial contamination so that the shelf life is longer/longer.
3. Aspects of business management and bookkeeping: Provided training with business management materials and technical preparation of simple bookkeeping which separates income and expenditure and separates business and household affairs and is given technical training on labor management and arranging job descriptions
4. Marketing Aspect: Marketing that has been done so far is still conventional, product marketing reach is still local and has not utilized social media and also have not used

online marketing. So the proposing team provides training on marketing strategy, provides input on marketing access by submitting products to both private and government agencies and provides training and assistance on the use of social media and online marketing in marketing products.

The implementation of this service has been carried out after the contract with the University of 17 August 1945 LPPM Surabaya. The initial stage was to coordinate with partners, namely Mrs. Niswatul Afifah in Minggirsari village, Blitar Regency regarding the implementation of training and assistance in making blended vegetable products. The production process is carried out at the Blendi vegetable processing site after the necessary tools are handed over to partners.

The partner previously made blended vegetables as usual, the results of which will later be compared with the results using the introduced tools, namely an electric oven and a vacuum sealer.

D. Conclusion

Various deficiencies in business managerial terms including aspects of marketing, finance, management of tools and distribution of business tasks are the focus of this service to increase the ability of residents to understand business technology developments to help develop SMEs in villages, especially UKM Blendi Yumi Sari through:

1. Providing technology in terms of drying blendi vegetables with an electric oven and a vacuum sealer for packaging with the aim of a longer shelf life.
2. Assistance with simple bookkeeping so that production money is separated from household money.

While suggestions for SMEs are:

1. The issue of a home industry permit (PIRT) has not been carried out, so assistance is needed to obtain the permit.
2. After getting the help of tools in the form of electric ovens and vacuum tools, it is recommended that MSMEs have more varied products.

With the dedication carried out by the University of 17 August 1945 Surabaya in Minggrisari Village, it is hoped that it will be able to arouse the enthusiasm of residents in entrepreneurship to turn the wheel of the village's local economy, moreover it can exist on the national stage.

E. References

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